

Tana Bhagats in Colonial and Postcolonial Times

Dr. Susmita Mohapatra

Assistant professor

YBN University, Jharkhand

Corresponding Author- Dr. Susmita Mohapatra

Email: drsumita1974@gmail.com

Abstract:

There were poignant moments during my visits to Ranchi, Lohardagga and Gumla, as I toured across the year 2012 some of the scattered pockets of Jharkhand where the rumbles of the Tana Bhagat movement can still be heard. I squirmed as my interlocutor, Sunitaji, who has been working for years amongst the Tana Bhagats and is now a member of the Gandhi Smriti and Darshan Samiti, introduced me: 'Didi Dillise aii hai. Bohut bara university me parati hai. Didi ek kitab likh rahi hai Tana Bhagat andoloan ke upar. Apna kahani batao. Didi ke prashn ka jawab do' (The elder sister has come from Delhi. She teaches in a very big university. She is writing a book on the Tana Bhagat movement. Tell her your story. Answer her questions). Delhi... University...Kitab (book)...Words that reinforced that distance between my informants and me which texts in critical anthropology had repeatedly alerted me to. 'Hum apse janne key liye aye hai' (I have come to learn from you), I hesitantly broke in. But Suktara Tana Bhagat, my octogenarian Tana informant, was not to be outdone; he inverted the unequal relationship between us in a moment. People from Delhi had visited him earlier too: they had come to him for information and guidance since they had wanted to make a film on the Tana Bhagats. He too had visited Delhi as part of a Tana delegation. Delhi, then, was not so remote for him, nor were we as researchers who wrote books or made films! But as I interacted with the Tana Bhagats, trying to understand adivasi movements in colonial and post-colonial times and thinking through the links between events/enactments, history, and the art of remembering and telling, I thought I should, as many of them had urged, tell their story. Though not as they would necessarily have liked me to tell it.

A twenty-five-year-old youth, Jatra Oraon of Gumla, Ranchi, proclaimed in April 1914 that he had received a divine message from Dharmes, the God of the Oraons. Jatra was to be a king and his followers,¹ the Tana Bhagats, were to share the kingdom. All those who did not join the movement, Jatra prophesied, would be struck dumb. Reciting what he claimed to be were divinely inspired mantras (devotional verses), Jatra advocated that Oraon religion should be freed of evils like ghost-finding and exorcism, belief in bhuts (spirits), animal sacrifice and drinking. His followers were to work no more as coolies or labourers; they were also to break the ploughs and stop the payment of rent to landlords. Ploughing fields entailed cruelty to cows and oxen, and had failed to save the Oraons from famine and poverty. God would provide for them, and a single grain of rice would satisfy a person's hunger. One or two small quadrangles were sufficient for the maintenance of an entire family: a handful of rice grains, if scattered on the land, would produce enough to fill a grain attic.² Because of the impending destruction of the world when earthly possessions would be the only hindrances, disciples of the faith were asked to purify themselves by discarding household equipments, agricultural implements and ornaments into the river.

Almost a hundred years has lapsed since then, and a hundred years is a long time. On October 1 and 2, 2012, I was in Bishunpur, Gumla, to witness what is today, for many, the most important event in the Tana calendar. On October 1, in the remote village of Chingri in Bishunpur where Jatra

Bhagat was born, and under his statue that had been erected in the 1989, about a hundred Tana Bhagats had assembled in the moonlit night.³ The chants of their mantras and the sound of the conch-shells pierced the stillness of the night; the smell of dhup (incense) was overpowering; the smoke made vision hazy. Clad in white sarees or kurtas (long shirts) made of khadi (hand-spun) cloth if they could afford it,⁴ and of synthetic if they could not, often with a Gandhi topi (cap) on their heads, wearing a janeu (sacred thread) or a thread around their necks, they clapped their hands as they chanted their invocations in obeisance to Jatra and Gandhi. As the chanting continued, some of the women got possessed. With their heads shaking, they bent before the image as they continued with the singing. On the following day, the birth anniversary of Gandhi, Gandhi Baba, the once-living and now deemed to be a powerful deity,⁵ was to be worshipped by them. The Tana Bhagats assembled at the same point in the morning; I was now familiar with the smoke, the smell of incense, the sound of the chanting and the clapping of hands. But this time, below the statue of Jatra Bhagat was placed a portrait of Gandhi. Linked then through this worship is Jatra Bhagat, the founder of the Tana Bhagat movement, with Gandhi, the 'Father of the nation'.

But there was little sense of the peace and quiet of the former night. On huge loudspeakers, one could hear the blare of patriotic songs from Hindi films, Hindi bhajans (devotional songs), and the voice of a member of the Vikas Bharati Bishunpur:⁶ 'The marathon is coming to a

close...the winner is coming in...please cheer loudly for him...the others will soon follow...'. The Vikas Bharati, a 'development agency' set up in 1983 under the initiative of Ashok Bhagat, Secretary of the organisation and an active 'social worker', with sympathies for the Hindu Right, concerned itself with educational, vocational and health-related interventions for 'the most neglected and remote communities of the state'. Every year around this time, as a means of mobilizing the adivasi youth under its fold, the Vikas Bharati organized cultural events, cycle races and marathons. Constructed very near the statue of Jatra Bhagat was a stage on which were huge portraits of Vivekananda, Gandhi and Jatra Bhagat. With bored and disinterested faces, the Tana Bhagats, who were now seated on chairs in the pandal (covered space constructed for festivities), sometimes clapped their hands as the participants of the marathon slowly trickled in. Others looked bewildered. The speeches began. Some prominent Tana Bhagat leaders were invited on stage to say a few words. And then spoke Ashok Bhagat: 'The non-violence that the Tana Bhagats preach is what we need today to fight the divisive forces in Jharkhand ...' 'Non-violence' is a Gandhian ideal that the Tana Bhagats claim for themselves, that links their past with Gandhi and that of the Indian nation.⁷ By tactically focusing on this, Ashok Bhagat could reconcile Tanas ideals and interests with the stated aim of the Vikas Bharati: to 'engage youths and mobilise them for the contributing to the nation-building and development of Jharkhand'.

The Tana Bhagat movement, then, is still alive, though the demands of the Tana Bhagats are today framed differently. A dwindling and yet visible community of about 10,000 people as they themselves speculate, their movement is fractured from within, with various groups articulating their grievances differently and advocating diverse paths for their agitation. For political parties, this group is numerically insignificant; their demands, although occasionally heard, are largely ignored as unpractical, absurd and beyond the scope of judicial and bureaucratic rationality. For the RSS, the Hindu Right, which is spreading its base amongst the adivasis, the Tana Bhagats, with their longer history of an opposition to the missionaries and their invoking of Gods and Goddesses from the 'Hindu' pantheon, are ideally suited for the battle against the ishais (Christians). From among the Tana community, some have tried their hands with electoral politics: Ganga Tana Bhagat was a 'vidhayak' (member of the state legislature) on a Congress ticket who had addressed some of the Tana grievances. The Congress, emphasising the Tana commitment to Gandhi and the Congress, has occasionally given them a hearing; inviting them for visits to Delhi were Rajendra Prasad, Jawaharlal Nehru, Indira Gandhi, Sonia Gandhi and in

September this year, Rahul Gandhi. But there are many others leading their ordinary lives in scattered pockets of Jharkhand. Caught between an almost lost past, a difficult present and an uncertain future, and finding many of their practices economically unviable to sustain, they carry on with their belief in Jatra Bhagat, the Mahatma, the Congress and the sarkar in Delhi. 'Jharkhand has just been formed', Suktara Tana Bhagat stated; 'Chhotanagpur and Bharat (India) have existed from the beginning.'⁸

This essay is on the Tana Bhagats in colonial and post-colonial times. I try and make sense of their movement in the colonial period, and then see how far the Tanas relate to the history of their movement – from the archives and as reconstructed by the historian – drawing as they do on the memories of events passed down generations, but carefully reworking these in conjunction with events relevant in the present context. While I have used an explanatory frame drawn from a historical perspective and engaged with the existing historiography on adivasi protest in colonial India, somewhere there is unease as the experiences of the Tana Bhagats cannot always be fitted into the frame of the historian. Indeed, studying adivasi movements only through the frame of the 'political' is itself limiting.⁹ By imposing through the flattened language of the 'modern' a singularity to events, it erases the multivocal and precludes thereby other possibilities, other voices, other touchstones, through which the Tanas made sense of their world. It gives a meaning to their everyday practices that cannot always be understood with the fair doses of rationality that the discipline of history requires of its practitioners. Rather than tying up my story, I therefore leave loose ends in my narrative recognizing the limits of history as an explanatory mode. Section I pieces together the many different stories of the Tanas and suggests a reading of adivasi resistance in colonial times; Section II analyses the movement in the phase 1914-1919; Section III explores the Tana relation with the Congress in the period following 1920; Section IV looks at the multiple ways in which the Tanas viewed their movement in post-colonial times.¹⁰ But my intention in following a chronological divide is not to etch out differences between phases as most historians have done while analysing the Tana Bhagat movement, but to argue against this.

How then are historical antecedents of adivasi resistance creatively worked out in post-colonial India? There are several pasts, not always mutually exclusive, that are in operation: at times historically framed, at times carefully crafted, at times consciously evocative; at times unconsciously structured. As Tana Bhagats negotiate

with a Tana past/ identity, an adivasi past/ identity and a nation's past/ identity, they express divergent voices and disparate dreams. Their

pamphlets begin with invocations to multiple images that cannot be quite reconciled, pointing to the fact that several pasts, several histories, several identities come into play in the making of the Tana Bhagats: Victory to Tana Religion! Victory to Mother Earth! Victory to Mother cow! Victory to Tana Bhagat Peasants! Victory to Mother India! Victory to

Mahatma Gandhi, Victory to National flag! In their self-depiction, the Tana Bhagats claim their identities at different levels. At times, they are a part of the nation's history as they talk about their participation in the national movement. They are, again, adivasis who share a sense of belonging and a common vocabulary of protest. 'The Mundas, Oraons and Kharias were...' is the way they often begin with their stories. And yet, they are not always so. They proclaim themselves to be Oraons, and often, more narrowly, Oraons who are against the *bhuinhars*, *pahans* and *mundas*, controllers of the ritual and economic worlds of the Oraons. As Anderson writes, the idea of the nation required people not only to expand their sense of community in new ways but in equally novel ways to constrict it.¹³⁶ For the Tana Bhagats, who today claim a political identity, this expansion and constriction of their community is a continual process. This paper on the Tana Bhagats thus, and here I quote selectively from Portelli, 'tries to convey the sense of fluidity, of unfinishedness...floating as it does in time between the present and an ever-changing past... and melting and coalescing in the no-man's land between orality to writing to back'

References :

1. S. C. Roy, *Oraon Religion and Customs* (Ranchi: 1928), p. 341.
2. Bihar and Orissa Government, Political Department, Special Section, File No. 54 of 1925.
3. A. John, 'Eine Reise nach Chechari' [A Journey to Chechari], *Die Biene auf dem Missions-felde für Missions-freunde und Missions Vereine*, No. 1, January. 1928, p. 64. This journal was the annual missionary journal of the German Evangelical Lutheran Mission (later renamed the Gossner Evangelical Lutheran Mission).
4. W. Dehmlow, 'Ein falscher Prophet in Bahar-Barwe' [A False Prophet in Bahar-Barwe], *Die Biene auf dem Missionsfelde*, No. 11, November, 1914, p. 151.
5. Vikas Bharati Bishunpur's '2010-11 Annual Report'.
6. See 'Secretary's Perspective', *Ibid.*, p. 1.
7. *Ibid.*, p. 43.
8. The term most commonly used to replace the category of the 'tribe' is that of 'adivasi', a term that came into use from the 1930s. While both these terms have their respective lineages, and

have come into use at different points of time, these are often used interchangeably and taken to be more or less synonymous. [See Introduction, B. G. Karlsson and T. Subba eds, *Indigeneity in India* (London: 2005), p. 2.] I however prefer to use 'adivasi'. [See D.J. Rycroft and S. Dasgupta, 'Indigenous Pasts and the Politics of Belonging' in D.J. Rycroft and S. Dasgupta eds, *The Politics of Belonging in India: Becoming Adivasi* (London and New York: 2011)].

9. See, for example, R. Guha's statement: 'For there was nothing in the militant movements of its (India's) rural masses that was not political' in R. Guha, *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India* (Delhi: 1983), p.6.
10. D. Chakrabarty, 'Minority Histories, Subaltern Pasts' in his *Provincializing Europe* (Princeton: 2000), pp. 97-116.